

COOLSCHOOLS: Realizing potentials of nature-based climate shelters in school environments for urban transformation

POLICY BRIEF FOR MINISTRIES OF EDUCATION: NATURE-BASED CLIMATE SHELTERS IN SCHOOLS

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Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Policy brief is informed by research done by the COOLSCHOOLS project, analysing the co-benefits of implementing nature-based solutions (NBS) for climate adaptation in “nature-based climate shelters in schools” (NBCSS). Along with best practices examined across four case study cities (Barcelona, Brussels, Paris, Rotterdam), findings were “translated” by the project into pedagogical resources (i.e. Guidelines for schools, a MOOC for teachers, and a user-friendly action plan to help educators plan schoolyard transformations or greening initiatives in schools). COOLSCHOOLS’ findings display in particular that NBCSS help withstand some of the heat-related effects of climate change for the benefit of students and the local school community. NBCSS also offer green connectors for biodiversity, and contribute to carbon sequestration, while tampering urban air pollution. On the educational level, NBCSS help grow the schoolyard into a new learning environment, support the introduction of green education into the STEM curriculum, and align with numerous international ambitions on education, sustainable development, climate adaptation and climate mitigation. This Policy brief will provide the reader with background information on NBCSS and connect teachers’ needs to actions that could be supported at national level by Ministries of Education: 1) support and optimize curriculum reform for the inclusion of green education; 2) recognize courses for Continuous Professional Development (CPD) national requirements/ create national CPD programs; 3) improve access to resources and tools, and endorse repositories/ include in national resources; 4) provide guidance for schools and encourage green transformations and collaboration; communicate local and international environmental ambitions and priorities. The Annex following these recommendations then showcases the resources for educators and schools that could be relayed by Ministries of Education and other educational policy professionals.

THE COOLSCHOOLS PROJECT

COOLSCHOOLS¹ is a transdisciplinary applied-research project that analyses the multiple co-benefits of implementing nature-based solutions (NBS)² for climate adaptation, in what we call “*nature-based climate shelters in schools*.”

In a very intuitive manner, introducing NBS in the urban school environment means creating green spaces using trees, vegetal surfaces, and soil to create shade and allow water to drain, while avoiding the absorption of heat.

The nature-based climate shelters advocated utilise green transformations rather than other building adaptations (such as the addition of air conditioning, or artificial structures, also known as “grey” transformations) to create school environments fit for a changing climate.

The approach of the project is two-fold:

- ⇒ First, **strengthen** academic knowledge on the value of green features for students and the school communities, and **understand** the experience and best practice resulting from school greening initiatives. Through extensive research, the COOLSCHOOLS academic team **investigated** the health, cognitive, and social benefits of transforming schoolyards into green spaces but also the co-benefits for biodiversity and climate resilience. By trying to understand how such transformation can support, and even guide urban transitions, our research also investigated processes, governance and participation in practical contexts.
- ⇒ Second, **translate** the best practice and academic knowledge into resources for teachers and schools, to encourage the widespread adoption of green schools, but also the dissemination of NBS and environmental knowledge. Creating a thriving ecosystem of resources, the pedagogical team produced a guide for schools, an online course, and a user-friendly four-step methodology to implement green activities based on the design thinking process. Seeking the **empowerment** of teachers, but also of the wider school community, the resources were designed to be accessible to all stakeholders.

The research and resources are based on the experience and best practice of **four case studies³ across Europe** which inform the work of COOLSCHOOLS, where municipalities have undertaken the transformation of many schoolyards into nature-based climate shelters. The four pioneer initiatives were

Figure 1. The COOLSCHOOLS framework

¹ <https://coolschools.eu/>

² NBS are defined by the European Union as: “Solutions that are inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social, and economic benefits and help build resilience. Such solutions bring more, and more diverse, nature and natural features and processes into cities, landscapes, and seascapes, through locally adapted, resource-efficient and systemic interventions. Nature-based solutions must therefore benefit biodiversity and support the delivery of a range of ecosystem services.”

³ Learn more: <https://coolschools.eu/case-studies/>

implemented by local governments in schools because of the widespread development of sustainability policies aiming to adapt cities to the future impact of climate change:

- Brussels Ose le vert (2016-2023), Opération Ré-création (2021-2024)
- Barcelona Climate Shelters in schools (2018-2021), Transformem els patis (2021-onwards)
- Paris Oasis (2018-onwards)
- Rotterdam Groenblauwe Schoolpleinen (2019-onwards).

EUROPEAN AND INTERNATIONAL POLICY CONTEXT

The green school transformations at the heart of the COOLSCHOOLS project align with both pedagogical and environmental international ambitions and strategies.

These strategies emphasise the importance of providing citizens (and children) with access to urban green spaces, in line with the **United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal (UN SDG)⁴ #11.7**, which envisions “*by 2030, to provide universal access to safe, inclusive and accessible green and public spaces, in particular for women and children, older persons and persons with disabilities*”.

Nature-based climate shelters in schools also align with the pedagogical ambitions of the UN, which, through its United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) has established the **Greening Education Partnership⁵**, with “*greening schools*” as one of the four pillars of its initiative for transformative education with the vision of working together “*From early childhood through adult education, (...) to ensure that all schools achieve green school accreditation, including teacher training and higher education institutions*”.

Contributing to local carbon sequestration but also working as shelter for biodiversity and as green connectors in urban environments, the vegetal spaces created in school can also contribute to the 2050 climate neutrality target of the **European Green Deal⁶**, and to the conservation ambitions of the **EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030⁷**.

NATURE-BASED CLIMATE SHELTERS IN SCHOOLS AND THEIR VALUE FOR STUDENTS (AND THE COMMUNITY)

A nature-based climate shelter is a green space in a school (more specifically, its schoolyard) that offers shelter from the impacts of climate change, heat mitigation, a healthier environment for the students daily, and an enhanced learning space to develop their cognitive skills and sustainability knowledge. Putting emphasis on education on NBS and bringing NBS to the public, an ever-growing number of projects⁸ have been funded by the European Commission in recent years that work in this field, establishing networks between various stakeholders, developing (education) materials, activities and trainings, as well as communities of practice for schools, organizations, initiatives, etc.

⁴ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

⁵ UNESCO's Greening Education Partnership: <https://www.unesco.org/en/sustainable-development/education/greening-future>

⁶ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

⁷ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/biodiversity-strategy-2030_en

⁸ Learn more about the range of projects on NBS here: https://rea.ec.europa.eu/funding-and-grants/horizon-europe-cluster-6-food-bioeconomy-natural-resources-agriculture-and-environment/nature-based-solutions_en

Such school transformations, initiated by a school through its leadership and administrative team, by teachers, or even by other members of the community, such as parents, provide long-term climate adaptation for the school and the students. The adaptation of the schoolyard helps schools, and their community withstand the daily impacts of climate change, all the while creating an enhanced learning and socialization space.

Figure 2. Example of green transformation in Parisian pre-school (C) CAUE Paris

THE BENEFITS OF GREEN SCHOOLYARDS

The following diagram summarizes the key benefits of green spaces in schools for students, the school community, and the environment. These findings and the methodologies are detailed in the academic publications⁹ produced during the project.

Figure 3. The numerous benefits of green schoolyards, as understood by COOLSCHOOLS.

⁹ See all the publications here: <https://coolschools.eu/publications/>

To learn more about education for climate resilience in urban environments, explore the **COOLSCHOOLS chapter** in the book *Urban Resilience to the Climate Emergency* (Springer)¹⁰.

A NOTE ON OPENING CLIMATE SHELTERS TO THE COMMUNITY

A common feature in the case studies' NBCSS is their accessibility to the community outside of school hours.

By opening these green spaces to the public when the school is not in session, nature-based climate shelters promote community engagement and social cohesion. They provide opportunities for people of all ages and backgrounds to connect with nature, fostering a sense of belonging and collective stewardship of the environment. Furthermore, access to green spaces offers an opportunity for residents to withstand extreme temperatures during climate change induced heat waves. Naturally, the opening of the schoolyard to the community remains the prerogative of each school, nevertheless, the value of providing such a space for the community cannot be understated.

NBS AND EDUCATION: GROWING THE SCHOOLYARD INTO A LEARNING SPACE

Nature-based climate shelters offer a range of pedagogical benefits, both during the design phase and in the long-term use of green spaces.

Firstly, **involving** the students in the design of the nature-based climate shelter helps them understand the benefits of green features in the urban landscape and the technological and natural solutions to climate change. In addition, getting the students to contribute to the design of the green space also enables them to collaborate on a common project, discuss, empathize, and express their thoughts and reasoning.

Furthermore, NBS as a topic presents the advantage of being **integrated** into a variety of school subjects, such as: science, technology, engineering, mathematics, arts, etc., as well as in any cross-curriculum education programme, furthering collaboration among the different subjects. To date, many projects exist that explore the integration of NBS into education, using a variety of approaches and methods, which would be supported by outdoor activities, such as the planning, designing and creation of nature-based climate shelters.

In the long term, providing students and teachers/educators with direct **access** to urban green spaces creates learning spaces to foster quality education on climate change in thematic areas such as wellbeing, safety, biodiversity conservation, inclusive decision making and other attributes. Such green spaces can become an experimental field for outdoor education, helping students develop a range of green competences, as defined in **GreenComp: The European Sustainability Competence framework**.¹¹

¹⁰ Read chapter in Open Access: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-07301-4_6

¹¹ https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/greencomp-european-sustainability-competence-framework_en

Figure 4. The pedagogical benefits of green schoolyards, as understood by COOLSCHOOLS.

HOW COULD MINISTRIES OF EDUCATION SUPPORT SCHOOLS IN GREENING INITIATIVES?

The capacity and overseeing of the schoolyard transformation process across Europe usually rests with local government and school authorities. **The action to transform the school grounds is therefore a local one.**

Nevertheless, central governments, and Ministries of Education in particular, have a key role to play in creating the impulse, nurturing the ambitions, and providing the guidance necessary for schools and educators to embrace green schoolyards and thus to unlock the various thematic benefits (see Figures 3 and 4) for students, the school community and the environment.

The following section translates teachers' and schools' needs into actions that could be supported at national level by Ministries of Education. In the annex following these recommendations, we also showcase the resources for educators and schools that could be relayed by educational policy professionals to enable the understanding of nature-based climate shelters.¹² Core recommendations and policy considerations are outlined in the table below, and elaborated on in the following sub-sections. e

¹² For recommendations for local policymakers and schools, please also refer to the COOLSCHOOLS guidelines for transformative governance in school climate shelters targeted for urban planners and local policymakers.

Table 1. Policy recommendations summary, based on teachers' and schools' needs.

Teachers' and Schools' Needs	Policy Recommendations
<p>Green schoolyards support sustainability and pedagogical ambitions (Green and Digital Transitions, GREEN COMP, SDGs). Green education also helps achieve a range of STEM and non-STEM learning objectives.</p>	<p> Support and optimize curriculum reform for the inclusion of green education</p>
<p>Teachers need knowledge and training to gain confidence in introducing environmental subjects in class.</p>	<p> Recognize courses for Continuous Professional Development (CPD) national requirements/ create national CPD programs</p>
<p>Teachers and schools need trustworthy resources to help them integrate new topics in class at all levels of education. Resources need to be adaptable and flexible.</p>	<p> Improve access to resources and tools and endorse repositories/ include in national resources</p>
<p>Teachers and schools need to be encouraged to transform their schoolyard and introduce new pedagogies. The greening of schoolyards and schoolground transformations will involve different stakeholders, experts, and levels of government.</p>	<p> Provide guidance for schools and encourage green transformations and collaboration. Communicate local and international environmental ambitions and priorities.</p>

1. SUPPORT AND OPTIMISE CURRICULUM REFORM FOR THE INCLUSION OF GREEN EDUCATION

Green schoolyards support sustainability and pedagogical ambitions that align with EU and member states' environmental and pedagogical ambitions.

A competence and values-based approach, green education helps achieve a range of STEM and non-STEM learning objectives, while developing core competences aligned with the GreenComp¹³ and LifeComp¹⁴ frameworks. Through green and outdoor education, students not only acquire vital skills and knowledge for them to contribute to a sustainable society, but they also learn to care for nature and gain agency in its conservation.

Green transformations can take various shapes and forms, starting from small non-structural transformations like green walls or potted vegetable gardens. All these transformations also enable STEM

¹³ GreenComp, the European sustainability competence framework, is available here: https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/greencomp-european-sustainability-competence-framework_en

¹⁴ LifeComp, the European framework for the personal, social and learning to learn key competence, is available here: https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/lifecom_en

and non-STEM learning experiences, helping students acquire a workable knowledge of the physical and natural processes.

As such, it is key to encourage the introduction of green education in the curriculum, thus encouraging educators to experiment with green education.

2. RECOGNISE COURSES THAT INTEGRATE ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION, NBS, AND GREEN SCHOOLYARDS FOR CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT (CPD) NATIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Teachers need knowledge and training to gain confidence in introducing environmental subjects in class. Lack of knowledge is one of the main obstacles to teachers and educators engaging with green transformations or environmental education.

This lack of knowledge can take multiple forms: environmental (environmental processes, ecosystem services), transversal (on other subjects in the curriculum, or on soft skills and competencies), or practical (from engaging with communities and professionals, to inadequate planting skills). As such, it is essential for education authorities to encourage teachers to upskill and develop their practice and innovate with green education by recognising their commitment and proactivity.

Such endorsement could include recognising EU-funded courses for CPD credits, integrating them into national courses, or even creating new courses that fit national circumstances when possible.

For example, the Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)¹⁵ created by COOLSCHOOLS in partnership with Scientix® and the European Schoolnet Academy, is published under the CC-BY4 creative commons license, making it possible for national authorities to translate, reuse and adapt all or parts of it to fit the needs of the education sector.

3. IMPROVE ACCESS TO TRUSTWORTHY RESOURCES AND TOOLS AND ENDORSE REPOSITORIES/ INCLUDE IN NATIONAL RESOURCES

Teachers and schools need trustworthy resources to help them integrate new topics in class at all levels of education and these resources need to be adaptable and flexible to fit local circumstances and national pedagogical agendas.

The education resources¹⁵ created by the COOLSCHOOLS project, such as the COOLSCHOOLS Guidelines for schools, the COOLSCHOOLS MOOC for teachers, as well as the COOLSCHOOLS Action plan for creating a nature-based climate shelter, along with the NBS and environmental resources created by other EU-funded projects, are designed to be adaptable to specific contexts and optimised to make replicating best practice easy. Furthermore, they include guidance and rationales to enable other users to adapt them to their context.

Created with academic experts for all educators and tested in practice, the resources are straightforward to endorse and can complement the pool of resources circulated in practicing teacher networks and teacher training programmes.

¹⁵ See Annex for more details.

4. PROVIDE GUIDANCE FOR SCHOOLS AND ENCOURAGE GREEN TRANSFORMATIONS AND COLLABORATION. COMMUNICATE LOCAL AND INTERNATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL AMBITIONS AND PRIORITIES

Teachers and schools need to be encouraged to transform their schoolyards, as well as given the space and time to experiment and collaborate. Meanwhile, they also require guidance to facilitate the process.

The greening of schools, and the general endeavour of introducing contextualised environmental knowledge, require the meaningful involvement of a variety of users, actors, and stakeholders. This may include all educators and school staff, local government policymakers and urban planners, but also school communities and technical experts and professionals (from architects to gardeners). Ministries of Education and national policy makers can contribute to the development of a **suitable policy framework for sustainable partnerships** between stakeholders involved in green education, green economy, and environmental conservation that can help facilitate the collaboration required for the greening of schoolyards and the general introduction of green education in schools.

Additionally, NBCSS have a role to play in helping cities adapt to the changing climate, making them a key tool in empowering students to become agents for societal change and a sustainable future. This in turn, requires educator to be aware and knowledgeable about such policy ambitions, mandating strong support from central government on relaying these ambitions. **Civic education classes, teacher- and student-friendly policy resources, and the participation of politicians, experts, professionals or community leaders in school activities are among some of the avenues available to generate strong engagement from students and educators on environmental and policy issues.** National school or teacher competitions can also be leveraged to encourage collaboration, environmental education, and citizen engagement.

ANNEX

RESOURCES FOR EDUCATORS

Here, we showcase the main COOLSCHOOLS tools and training for teachers and other education community actors. These tools could be endorsed and relayed by the Ministries of Education. Built from trustworthy academic sources and co-created with pedagogical experts and practicing educators, these resources could be integrated into national resource repositories, teachers' networks, and pre- and in-service teacher training programmes.

These resources are also available through **the Scientix® Repository of Resources**.

Go to www.scientix.eu to access them, and thousands more tools and resources for STEM and NBS education.

THE COOLSCHOOLS GUIDELINES FOR SCHOOLS

These Guidelines help school leaders, teachers, and community members such as parents understand the practical steps and considerations to plan and design the transformation of the schoolyard into a nature-based climate shelter. A Nature-Based Climate Shelter is a green space in the schoolyard that can be opened to the community during extreme weather events such as heatwaves. Nature-based climate shelters offer a range of benefits for health, learning, social cohesion, and biodiversity. The advice provided is based on the experience of four case-study cities (Barcelona, Brussels, Paris, Rotterdam), where municipalities have undertaken the transformation of many schoolyards as part of their climate resilience strategy.

Read and disseminate the Guidelines for schools:

Grand-Meyer, E et al. (2024) “The COOLSCHOOLS Guidelines for schools: how to turn your schoolyard into a nature-based climate shelter”, February 2024, European Schoolnet, Brussels. Accessible online via:

<https://www.scientix.eu/resources/details?resourceId=130261>

THE COOLSCHOOLS MASSIVE OPEN ONLINE COURSE

Created in partnership with and hosted on the European Schoolnet Academy, this course was designed to help teachers learn how to implement nature-based climate shelter interventions in the classroom with a design-thinking approach. The COOLSCHOOLS and Scientix® “*Nature-based Climate Shelters in Schools: Empowering Teachers for Sustainable Education*” MOOC is tailored for educators interested in student-centered learning and climate change adaptation. The MOOC explores concepts like NBS, nature-based climate shelters and urban nature-based solutions, and enables participants to understand and develop greening activities in schools.

Discover the MOOC and register (available without certification):

<https://www.europeanschoolnetacademy.eu/courses/course-v1:COOLSCHOOLS+GreenSchools+2024/about>

Read the report on the course and its impact on participants:

Tezas, N., Ivanova, I., & Gras-Velazquez, A. (2024). *Nature-based climate shelters in schools: empowering teachers for sustainable education*” MOOC Report. Zenodo. Accessible online via: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14001772>

THE COOLSCHOOLS ACTION PLAN: FOUR STEPS TO A GREEN SCHOOLYARD

The COOLSCHOOLS action plan has been designed to accommodate educators in the implementation of NBCSS and urban NBS, while involving students in the designing and implementation process. By applying the design thinking approach to the planning of climate shelter interventions and other greening activities in schools, the template provides an accessible framework for educators to structure their NBS activities inside and outside of the classroom. Step-by-step guidance on creating the Action Plan is available in the COOLSCHOOLS MOOC (as presented above).

Discover and share the COOLSCHOOLS Action Plan:

http://files.eun.org/scientix/COOLSCHOOLS_Action-Plan_template.docx

